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Executive summary

This internal report on recommendation for microbiome analysis standards aims to outline and briefly explain the landscape of the current analysis methods in the human microbiome field. It includes the preprocessing, primary, and secondary analysis of metagenomic, metatranscriptomic, metaproteomic, and metabolomic data, and ends with a description of integrated multi-omic analysis. This report also incorporates the input from experts, collected from the WP3 “Workshop on Establishing Consensus for Microbiome Analysis Standards” held on 20th September 2023 at EMBL Heidelberg.

Report on Recommendations for Microbiome analysis standards

Introduction

Extensive research into the human gut microbiome has revealed significant associations between microbial compositions and a range of health conditions. This growing recognition of the microbiome's influence on health has spurred enhanced efforts to collect, preserve, and analyze various microbiome samples, such as feces, saliva, and skin swabs. Contemporary state-of-the-art omics analyses involve characterizing the complete molecular profile of microbiome samples, encompassing genomic (metagenomics), transcriptomic (metatranscriptomics), metabolomic (metabolomics), and proteomic (metaproteomics) aspects. Therefore, this report will focus on these four types of omic data analysis.

Microbiome analyses generally encompass three key stages: 1) ensuring quality control of raw data; 2) conducting primary analysis on this curated data; and 3) performing secondary analysis based on the initial findings. Preprocessing raw data for quality control is vital for minimizing biases in subsequent results that may arise from technical discrepancies, ensuring a true reflection of the underlying biological conditions. Primary analysis methods utilize these quality-controlled data to generate new genomic information or compute quantitative results. For instance, microbiome profiling tools are instrumental in obtaining a detailed quantitative representation of specific microbial communities. Secondary analysis methods then take the outputs from primary analysis (e.g., quantitative or categorical profiles of the microbiomes) and employ hypothesis testing, biomarker discovery, phylogenetic analysis, and ecological and epidemiological models to link outcomes of interest with these profiles.

A variety of standardized computational pipelines are available for primary or secondary microbiome data analysis, each offering unique advantages and limitations. While this abundance of choice meets the needs of a wide variety of users, it also hinders easy comparisons across multiple studies that use different pipelines. Here, we identify currently available software (pipeline) choices to perform microbiome analysis. Our goal is to provide comprehensive guidelines and best practices, focusing on a holistic approach rather than prescribing a single solution for each task.

Metagenomic and metatranscriptomic data are generated using DNA sequencing techniques. Thus, they can both be handled using similar computational approaches during the quality control stage, and to a large extent also during the primary analysis stage. Similarly, metabolomic and metaproteomic data derive from mass spectrometry techniques and thus share computational approaches during the quality control stage. However, primary analysis approaches differ significantly between metabolomic and metaproteomic data. Since secondary analysis focuses on generic insights, such as hypothesis testing and biomarker discovery, the same computational approaches can be applied to all four omic data types. We briefly introduce the two different kinds of data that we discuss in this report.

Sequencing data from metagenomics and metatranscriptomics

Metagenomic sequencing and metatranscriptomic sequencing are powerful techniques used to characterize the collective genome and the active gene expression, respectively, of microbial communities in various environments.

Metagenomic sequencing focuses on analyzing the genetic material recovered directly from environmental samples. This technique allows for the characterization of the complete set of genes (the metagenome) present in a microbial community, regardless of the ability to culture these microbes in the laboratory. It involves extracting and sequencing DNA from a sample, such as soil, water, or a human gut sample, and then using bioinformatics tools to assemble and analyze the sequences. This approach provides insights into the diversity, structure, and potential functions of microbial communities, enhancing our understanding of microbial ecology and evolution.

Metatranscriptomic sequencing, on the other hand, targets the RNA molecules (specifically mRNA) in a sample, to understand the active gene expression of the microbial community at the time of sampling. This technique involves extracting RNA, converting it into cDNA, and then sequencing it. Metatranscriptomics offers a snapshot of the functional activity of the microbial community, revealing which genes are being actively transcribed and potentially translated into proteins. This helps in understanding the dynamic response of microbes to environmental changes, their metabolic activities, and their roles in various ecosystems.

Both metagenomic and metatranscriptomic sequencing leverage next-generation sequencing technologies, enabling the comprehensive analysis of complex microbial communities. They provide valuable insights into the functional potential and actual activity of microbes, respectively, playing crucial roles in fields like environmental microbiology, human health, and biotechnology.

Mass spectrometry data from metabolomics and metaproteomics

Metabolomics and metaproteomics have gained significant traction in recent years with respect to microbiome research, especially in the context of “multi omic” data. Even though other approaches such as nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR) are available to characterize small molecule metabolites and proteins, chromatography-coupled mass spectrometry has emerged as the most commonly used approach.

Chromatography-coupled mass spectrometry has emerged as a pivotal tool in metabolomics and proteomics, gaining popularity for its exceptional ability to analyze complex biological samples. This technique offers high sensitivity and specificity, crucial in metabolomics for identifying and quantifying small molecules or metabolites, thereby illuminating metabolic pathways and biochemical processes. In proteomics, it plays a key role in characterizing and quantifying proteins, providing insights into cellular functions and disease mechanisms. The integration of chromatographic separation with mass spectrometry's precise molecular detection facilitates the comprehensive profiling of thousands of biomolecules, even in low concentrations, making it invaluable for biomarker discovery and therapeutic development.

Delving into the specifics, chromatography-coupled mass spectrometry combines chromatography, a method for separating mixtures based on different physical or chemical properties of compounds, with mass spectrometry, which identifies and quantifies molecules based on their mass-to-charge ratio (m/z). In the initial chromatographic phase, compounds in a sample are separated due to their varying interactions with a stationary phase or their differential solubility in a mobile phase. Following separation, the mass spectrometer ionizes these compounds and measures how they behave in an electric or magnetic field, thus determining their mass-to-charge ratio and recording their retention time associated with the separation. This dual approach, encompassing both qualitative (identifying the constituents) and quantitative (measuring the amounts of each component) analysis, is widely applied in biochemistry, environmental testing, and pharmacology. Its ability to detect, identify, and quantify low levels of diverse compounds in various samples solidifies its status as a central technique in modern biochemical and pharmaceutical research.

Most commonly used combinations are:

1. **Gas Chromatography-Mass Spectrometry (GC-MS):** This combines gas chromatography (GC) for separating volatile compounds and mass spectrometry for compound detection and quantification. It is widely used in forensic science, environmental testing, and drug discovery.

2. **Liquid Chromatography-Mass Spectrometry (LC-MS):** In this technique, liquid chromatography (LC) separates compounds dissolved in a liquid phase, and these separated compounds are then analyzed by mass spectrometry. LC-MS is particularly useful in pharmaceuticals, metabolomics, and proteomics.

Quality control of raw data

Preprocessing and quality control (QC) of raw omic data are fundamental steps in the analysis of human microbiome data, essential to ensure data integrity. This crucial process guarantees that the analyzed data accurately represents the microbial community, making it suitable for reliable subsequent analyses.

Handling sequencing data

As both metagenomics and metatranscriptomics depend on sequencing data, they share essential QC measures in raw data preprocessing. This can be performed using two complementary approaches:

1. Using data characteristics

The preprocessing of sequencing reads involves three key steps:

- **Removal of Primer or Adapter Sequences:** The first step involves removing primer or adapter sequences from the sequenced reads. Concurrently, all low-quality reads are discarded. Optionally, reads shorter than a predetermined minimum length can be excluded, depending on the goals of the downstream analysis.
- **Exclusion of Contaminant DNA:** The second step focuses on removing DNA contaminants. For human microbiome samples, human DNA is often an undesired contaminant and should be excluded by mapping reads against the human genome. Laboratory environment contaminant sequences may also be excluded if tracked. Additionally, other DNA contaminants, like spike-in DNA introduced during sequencing, must be verified. For example, in Illumina sequencing, the PhiX bacteriophage genome is used for run quality control.
- **Handling Unpaired Reads in Paired-End Sequencing:** The third step, applicable for paired-end sequencing, involves separating paired reads from unpaired ones, which could arise from the previous quality control steps. This is particularly important for analyses that benefit from paired-end information, like metagenomic assembly methods.

2. Using positive and negative control samples

In designing microbiome analysis studies, incorporating an adequate number of positive and negative controls is critical. This ensures the identification and elimination of potential contaminants and batch effects introduced during various stages such as handling, storage, DNA extraction, and sequencing platforms (Salter *et al.*, 2014); (Minich *et al.*, 2019). Specifically, contamination is a major issue in low biomass samples or samples massively contaminated by human DNA, such as skin swabs or rectal swabs, and must be addressed in such samples.

- **Positive Controls:** Typically, commercially available mock communities containing known concentrations and/or proportions of bacteria and fungi are used. These should be prepared at various dilutions (e.g., 10^{-2} , 10^{-4} , and 10^{-6}) to facilitate the detection of potential contaminants from manipulations and consumables ((Karstens *et al.*, 2019) ; Barcenilla *et al.*, 2023 {not doi yet}).
- **Negative Controls:** These may include open-air bags for swabbing or sterile water and should undergo the same nucleic acid extractions as the actual samples (Barcenilla *et al.*, 2023 {not doi yet}). They help in identifying contaminants introduced during handling, storage, and sequencing.

Software tools for sequence decontamination

Various software tools, such as decontam (Davis *et al.*, 2018) and KneadData {CIT}, are available for the in silico identification and removal of contaminant reads. Decontam, for instance, identifies contaminants based on their frequency and prevalence in negative controls compared to actual samples, while KneadData {CIT} performs quality control of sequencing reads and excludes reads matching human and host genomes or custom user-defined databases.

Ultimately, this preprocessing phase concludes with the meticulous removal of reads that are either technical artifacts, of low quality, or contaminants, including those originating from the host genome.

Handling mass spectrometry data

QC in handling chromatography-coupled MS data is vital to ensure the accuracy and reliability of the results.

1. Using data characteristics

Some quality control steps rely on the inherent nature of the MS data and noise patterns. The following quality control steps are included in handling MS data:

- **Replicate Analyses:** Analyzing replicates of samples can help in assessing the precision and reproducibility of the method. This includes both technical replicates (same sample analyzed multiple times) and biological replicates (different samples from the same group).
- **Data Processing and Deconvolution:** The raw data obtained needs to be processed and analyzed carefully. This includes peak identification, deconvolution, and integration, followed by a rigorous review to ensure correct peak assignment and quantification.
- **Software-Based QC Checks:** Modern chromatography and mass spectrometry systems are often equipped with softwares that provide automatic QC checks, including calculation of signal-to-noise ratios, retention time stability, and peak shape analysis.
- **Data Normalization:** Particularly important in comparative studies, data normalization (such as using the total ion count) helps in reducing variability due to sample preparation or instrumental differences.

2. Using standard, positive and negative control samples

Some QC steps are based on the expected behavior of control samples and statistically correct deviations from expectations. The following standards are recommended during each batch of chromatography-coupled MS analysis:

- **Use of Internal Standards:** Internal standards, compounds with known properties, are often added to each sample. These standards provide a reference point for quantitation and help in monitoring the consistency of the analytical process.
- **Blank Samples:** Running blank samples (samples without analytes) helps in identifying any contamination or carryover from previous samples. Blanks should show no peaks for the analytes of interest.
- **Quality Control Samples:** These are samples with known concentrations of analytes, ran at regular intervals during the analysis. They help in monitoring the stability and performance of the analytical system over time.

Challenges in recognizing identical molecules between different batches

Identifying the same molecules across different batches using only mass-to-charge ratio (m/z) and retention time in chromatography-coupled mass spectrometry can be challenging due to several factors (Liu *et al.*, 2020). The m/z ratio, while a critical identifier, can sometimes be insufficiently specific, especially when dealing with complex mixtures where different compounds might have similar or even identical m/z values. This issue, known as isobaric interference, can lead to ambiguous identifications. Additionally, retention times can vary between batches due to

slight changes in chromatographic conditions, such as column aging, flow rate alterations, or temperature fluctuations. These variations can result in shifts in retention times, making it difficult to confidently match peaks across different runs. The problem is compounded in biological samples, where matrix effects can alter both the ionization efficiency (affecting m/z measurements) and the chromatographic behavior (affecting retention times) of molecules. Without additional layers of data, such as fragmentation patterns (MS/MS spectra) or the use of standards, relying solely on m/z and retention time can lead to uncertainties in molecule identification, necessitating more comprehensive approaches for accurate batch-to-batch comparison.

Current approaches involve matching the m/z ratios and retention times using instrument-specific error margins, using software programs from the providers or publicly available software (Schmid *et al.*, 2023). Novel machine learning algorithms are being developed to analyze complex patterns within the data, enhancing the accuracy of molecule identification based on m/z ratios, retention times, and ionization patterns, such as the recently published DeepRTAlign (Y. Liu *et al.*, 2023) approach. With the field rapidly evolving, the problem of batch effects will hopefully be addressed to a large extent in the next decade.

Primary Analysis Methods

Primary analysis methods are a cornerstone in microbiome data processing, utilizing quality-controlled data to generate summary outputs. These outputs are crucial as they summarize key components of interest within a microbiome sample. For instance:

- **Abundances of Different Species:** This analysis quantifies the presence of various microbial species in a sample, providing insights into the microbial diversity and potential dominance of certain species in a given host.
- **Concentrations of Different Bile Acids:** Bile acid analysis helps understand the metabolic interactions within the microbiome and its impact on the host's digestive system.
- **Gene Expression Profiles of Specific Functional Pathways:** This analysis sheds light on the active metabolic or signaling pathways in the microbiome, revealing how microbes interact with each other and their environment.
- **Levels of Different Mobile Genetic Elements:** Understanding the distribution and levels of mobile genetic elements, such as plasmids or transposons, can offer insights into genetic transfer and antibiotic resistance patterns.

The data generated from these analyses are fundamental for downstream applications. They enable robust statistical analysis and hypothesis testing, forming the basis for understanding the complex interactions within the microbiome and its impact on health and disease. By providing a detailed picture of the microbiome's composition and activity, primary analysis methods lay the groundwork for comprehensive and insightful studies.

Primary analysis of sequencing data

Primary analysis of sequencing data in microbiome studies is pivotal, as it generates essential summaries for understanding the composition and function of microbial communities. This analysis is typically categorized into two types: microbiome taxonomic profiles and microbiome functional profiles. Both types depend on comparing microbial genomes to discern similarities/differences for taxonomy assignment and to annotate functions. Accordingly, primary analysis methods are categorized into two groups: utilizing existing databases/resources of known genomes and generating de novo genomes from a sample.

Using Existing Genome Resources

Large genome databases, like GenBank, are instrumental for deciphering species present in each microbiome sample. Several software tools simplify this process by consolidating vast genome collections and enabling profiling against these databases.

1. Taxonomic Profiling Using Existing Genomes

Taxonomic profiling methods that leverage existing genome resources generally fall into three categories:

- **Full-genome Matching:** This approach maps sequence reads against predefined genome databases, like the Integrated Microbial Genomes & Microbiomes (IMG/M) resource (Chen *et al.*, 2022). In theory, this method offers the highest precision and recall, contingent on the comprehensiveness of the genome database. However, it's no longer computationally efficient with next-generation sequencing generating millions of short reads.
- **K-mer-based Approaches:** These methods aim to approximate full-genome matching by creating databases of k-mers and their frequencies in large genome databases. Metagenomic reads are then reduced to k-mers and mapped to the reference k-mer database. Tools like Kraken, Kaiju, GANON, and MetaCache employ this approach. They retain much of the sensitivity of full-genome matching methods, but careful parameter selection is imperative to limit false positives.

- **Marker-Gene-Based Approaches:** Utilizing specific genes for taxonomic classification, these methods include multiple universally conserved single-copy marker genes (mOTUs), clade-specific genes for identifying specific microbial lineages (MetaPhlAn), and single marker sequences (like 16S rRNA gene or its subregions). While multiple marker genes or clade-specific genes necessitate shotgun metagenomic sequencing, single marker sequences can be obtained cost-effectively using amplicon-sequencing. These methods are highly accurate but depend greatly on the extent of reference database coverage. Taxonomy assignment for novel species without close relatives in the databases can be unreliable or impossible.

2. Functional Profiling Using Existing Genomes

Functional profiling can also be segmented into two categories:

- **Inferring Functions from Taxonomy:** These methods use predetermined functional signatures of microbes from different taxonomic lineages to infer the functional composition of a microbiome from its taxonomic profile. This is typically done on 16S amplicon-based taxonomic profiles, with PICRUSt2 being a prominent tool used for inferring functions from human microbiome samples.
- **Functional Profiling from Sequence Reads:** Direct analysis of shotgun metagenomic reads is performed by comparing them against functional databases. HUMAnN is a notable example, providing functional composition as defined by the MetaCyc pathway database.

Using *de novo* assembled genomes

In situations where existing databases inadequately represent a microbiome sample, or when a higher resolution is needed, *de novo* assembly of microbial genomes from shotgun metagenomic or metatranscriptomic samples becomes essential. These metagenome-assembled genomes (MAGs) offer valuable insights into the genomic content of microbes in a sample.

Generating MAGs

The generation of MAGs involves several critical steps:

- **Metagenomic Assembly:** This process aligns and merges shotgun sequencing reads into contigs, aiming to reconstruct portions of the original genomes. Tools like MetaSPAdes, Megahit, and Flye are commonly used in this step.

- **Metagenomic Binning:** This step clusters metagenomic contigs, likely originating from the same genome, into bins to reconstruct (near-)complete genomes. Tools such as MetaBAT2, MaxBin2, CONCOCT, VAMB, and SemiBin2 facilitate this process. Subsequent quality assessment with tools like CheckM is vital.

Challenges in Generating MAGs

Generating de novo MAGs is fraught with challenges:

- **Estimation Errors:** Tools like CheckM estimate genome completeness and contamination but can sometimes lead to false estimates, resulting in incorrect MAGs.
- **Species Abundance:** High-quality MAGs require the species to be sufficiently abundant for extensive genome coverage.
- **Dataset Size:** The quality of MAGs is also linked to the size of the metagenome dataset being binned together, putting smaller datasets at a disadvantage.
- **Handling Mobile Genetic Elements (MGEs):** Current binning algorithms struggle with the complexity of MGEs.

Similar to whole-genome sequencing (WGS) analysis of single genomes, open-source software like TORMES, ASA3P, Bactopia, and Nullarbor can be employed for automated genome analysis.

Taxonomic Profiling Using MAGs

Taxonomic profiles derived from MAGs necessitate analyzing their phylogenetic origins. Tools like PhyloPhlAn or GTDB-tk are instrumental in this process, enabling the conversion of MAG abundance profiles into taxonomic profiles.

Functional Profiling Using MAGs

This step involves annotating genes from MAGs using databases such as KEGG, eggNOG, and CAZy. These annotations allow the conversion of gene abundance profiles into functional profiles.

In summary, the primary analysis of sequencing data offers insightful glimpses into the microbial world by profiling both the taxonomy and function of microbiomes. The choice of method depends on various factors including computational resources, desired level of detail, and the specific objectives of the study.

Primary analysis of spectrometry data

Primary analysis of metaproteomic and metabolomic data involves primarily the annotation of processed MS data. The main task is the identification of spectrometric read-outs, and matching them to metabolites/peptides for which reference peaks exist. There are various reference databases one could use, for example GNPS (Wang *et al.*, 2016)(Y. Liu *et al.*, 2023), and also for de-novo peptide sequence identification for MS-MS data (K. Liu *et al.*, 2023)

The common steps involved here are :

- Identification - This takes as input the pre-processed clean peak data, and uses reference databases to match peaks and retention times to existing metabolites, to estimate their abundance in the sample
- Annotation - From the identified features of the sample, annotation involves the grouping of metabolites into groups, either by their structure (eg steroid like), or their function (eg, involved with glucose metabolism), using ontologies such as KEGG.

Secondary Analysis Methods

Quantitative or qualitative profiles, typically derived from primary analysis methods, serve as inputs for secondary analysis methods. They provide a summary of different features of interest identified/quantified in an individual sample. The focus of secondary analysis is generally on addressing biological queries by investigating connections between these profiles and sample metadata.

Important aspects of secondary analysis

Some key aspects to consider during secondary analysis of microbiome data are:

1. Sample and subject metadata

The term "metadata" refers to comprehensive data encompassing both the characteristics of the microbiome sample and the human subject from whom it was obtained. This includes:

- **Sample Characteristics:** Type, collection procedure, storage, and handling history.
- **Subject Metadata:** Encompasses a broad spectrum of data:
 - **Demographic Data:** Age, sex, gender, socioeconomic status.
 - **Anthropometric Data:** Height, weight, body mass index, body fat percentage.

- **Behavior/Lifestyle Data:** Dietary patterns, physical activity, smoking, alcohol consumption.
- **Medical History:** Surgeries, hospitalization, symptom reports like pain and fatigue.
- **Treatment and Medication:** Information on treatment dates, dosages, and disease progression.
- **Physical Examination Data:** Temperature, blood pressure, heart rate.
- **Laboratory Test Data:** Results from biological samples like blood, urine, or stool.
- **Other Health Data:** Sleep patterns and additional well-being indicators.

2. Profiles of individual vs aggregate features

Secondary analysis utilizes both individual and aggregated feature profiles from microbiome samples:

- **Individual Feature Profiles:** This includes detailed data such as the relative abundance of microbial strains (metagenomic), gene expressions (metatranscriptomic), metabolite levels (metabolomic), and peptide quantities (metaproteomic).
- **Aggregate Feature Profiles:** These summarize higher-level features for better biological interpretation and to simplify analysis. Examples include the combined abundance of microbial phyla (metagenomic), community-wide expression of functional pathways (metatranscriptomic), grouped concentrations of metabolites like bile acids (metabolomic), and community-wide representation of gene ontology terms (metaproteomic).

3. Ecological summaries from feature profiles

In human microbiome studies, ecological principles provide crucial insights at the community level. Two primary ecological metrics stand out:

1. **Alpha Diversity:** This metric explores the variety and abundance of microbial species within each individual sample. It helps to gauge the complexity and health of the microbiome within a single environment.
2. **Beta Diversity:** This measurement compares the microbial communities across different samples, revealing variations and similarities in microbiome composition between individuals or conditions.

Together, alpha and beta diversity offer a comprehensive picture of the microbiome's structure and function, significantly enhanced by integrating sample-specific metadata.

4. Feature normalization

Normalization of microbiome data is a critical step in ensuring accurate and meaningful analysis:

- **Preprocessing:**

The data, typically presented as feature matrices (like read counts or metabolite abundances), undergoes preprocessing to establish feature inclusion/exclusion criteria and mitigate experimental biases. Feature selection based on minimum abundance/concentration across all samples or prevalence in the set of samples can help in reducing noisy features and provide improved statistical power depending on the analysis that follows.

- **Data Transformation Techniques:**

Profile data from primary analysis can still suffer from caveats that prevent the proper use of statistical analysis. For example, certain type of data may not be normally distributed in the raw profiles but could be near-normal once log-transformed. In this situation, only log-transformed data should be analyzed using the Student's *t*-test, which expects data to be normal. Depending on the type of data, there are several such data transformation steps that are necessary:

- **Rarefaction:** Applied to sequencing data, this technique ensures equitable comparisons across samples, accounting for varying sequencing depths. It was popular during the early days of 16S rRNA gene amplicon sequencing studies but the current consensus is to not apply rarefaction (McMurdie and Holmes, 2014).
- **Log-Ratio Transformations:** Sequencing-based relative abundance data are compositional in nature: true abundances of features are not known, only relative abundances are. This makes it complicated to compare values across samples. In such cases, ratios between features is a more reliable measure that can be compared across samples. Techniques like centered log-ratio (CLR) and additive log-ratio (ALR) are utilized to address the compositional nature of microbiome data and mitigate negative correlation biases.
- **Zero Imputation:** The prevalence of zeros in microbiome data necessitates careful consideration in transformation, impacting subsequent analyses.
- **Handling Non-Linear Characteristics:** Some data types exhibit non-linear behavior. Methods like arcsine square-root or inverse normal rank-based transformations are employed to address these non-linear traits of microbiome profiles.

Secondary analysis types

Secondary analysis can be put into broad categories that provide a unique perspective on the complex relationship between the microbiome and human health, particularly in the context of disease. These are:

1. **Hypothesis Testing and Validation:** Involves statistical methods to test and validate hypotheses derived from microbiome data, such as differences in microbial communities under various conditions.
2. **Association and Correlation Analysis:** Seeks to uncover correlations between microbial profiles and health states, identifying potential causal relationships between the microbiome and diseases.
3. **Biomarker Discovery:** Focuses on identifying specific microbial signatures that can act as biomarkers for health conditions, aiding in early detection or monitoring of diseases.
4. **Classification and Predictive Modeling:** Utilizes machine learning and statistical models to classify subjects based on their microbiome profiles or to predict outcomes like disease progression, or response to treatment.
5. **Enrichment and Functional Analysis:** Analyzes data to understand the functional implications of the microbiome, such as metabolic pathway enrichment, gene function, and microbial interactions within the host.
6. **Temporal and Spatial Analysis:** Examines changes in the microbiome over time or across different body sites in relation to disease development and progression.
7. **Network Analysis:** Involves studying the complex interactions and relationships within microbial communities, often using graphical models to understand community structure and inter-species dependencies, to understand disease dynamics, such as how certain microbial communities influence disease states.
8. **Comparative Genomics:** Analyzes microbial genomes to understand genetic factors that may contribute to disease susceptibility or resistance, and microbial diversity in disease versus healthy states.

Recommendations when performing secondary analysis

The first five types are most commonly used by microbiome researchers. Therefore, we provide caveats and recommendations based on the expert discussions in the next section.

1. **Hypothesis Testing and Validation:** Caveats include overfitting, use of wrong models (mismatch between model and data), and multiple testing issues. Recommendations include using stringent statistical correction methods and cross-validation techniques.

2. **Association/Correlation Analysis:** Potential pitfalls are confounding factors and false correlations. Recommendations include careful selection of control groups and use of robust statistical models to account for confounders.
3. **Biomarker Discovery:** Challenges involve distinguishing true biomarkers from coincidental associations. Recommendations include validating findings across diverse populations and using longitudinal studies for stronger evidence.
4. **Classification & Predictive Modeling:** Risks include model overfitting and biased training data. It's recommended to use diverse datasets for training models and their validation externally.
5. **Enrichment & Functional Analysis:** Potential issues include misinterpretation of data due to incomplete reference databases. Researchers should use updated databases and integrate multiple omics data for comprehensive analysis.

Awareness of these pitfalls and adherence to best practices can significantly enhance the reliability and validity of research findings in microbiome studies.

Integration of Multi-omic Data

The landscape of microbiome research is undergoing a transformative shift with the adoption of multi-omic analysis. Instead of scrutinizing individual omic data sets in isolation, researchers now harness the collaborative potential by merging information from metagenomes, metatranscriptomes, metaproteomes, and metabolomes. This integrated approach enhances the depth and breadth of our understanding of the microbiome's composition, functions and interactions with the host.

There are two primary strategies for multi-omic integration:

Independent Analysis and Integrated Interpretation: This approach involves analyzing each omic data type independently and interpreting the combined results. For instance, metagenomic, metatranscriptomic, and metaproteomic data are scrutinized separately, and their collective insights yield a more holistic understanding of the microbiome.

Integrated Analysis and Interpretation: A more sophisticated approach involves fully integrating the analysis, incorporating molecular connections across omes during the process. This aligns with the fundamental principles of molecular biology: DNA → RNA → protein → metabolites. By establishing associations within and between different “omes” using statistical methods or existing biological

knowledge, this method enables researchers to draw meaningful inferences about the relationships among multi-omic features.

To qualify as an "integrated" multi-omic analysis, a study must conduct an "integrated analysis" of data from at least metagenomic, metatranscriptomic, metaproteomic, and metabolomic data types (Heintz-Buschart *et al.*, 2016). The inclusion of additional data types, such as "omes" from different host body sites or imaging data, can further enhance the integrated analysis. This holistic approach empowers researchers to uncover more robust associations and insights by considering the molecular flow from genes to metabolites.

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